

iRiis

Logo Manual

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This guide is designed to help us use correctly the IRIS logo. It will also be useful aid when instructing typographers and others employed to produce branded items, to design and create IRIS communications material.

In order to maintain the integrity of our identity and what it represents it is important to apply all the elements of the toolkit properly and consistently.

Concept / The idea behind

The IRIS project logo focuses on its technological dimension through a minimalist approach, giving the project's character as simple and concise as possible for its optimum usability in any visual communication action required.

Vision: Uptake of IoT and AI driven ICT systems in Europe is crucial for our common future, but it is dependent on our strategic ability to protect these systems from cyber threats and attacks on their privacy. IRIS aims to integrate and demonstrate a single platform addressed to CERTs/CSIRTs for assessing, detecting, responding to and sharing information regarding threats & vulnerabilities of IoT and AI-driven ICT systems.

IRIS will contribute towards a European strategic autonomy in IoT and AI cybersecurity and provide a dynamic, holistic and disruptive security-enabling solution for minimizing the attack surface in these complex ICT systems

SUMMARY

Uptake of IoT and AI driven ICT systems in Europe is crucial for our common future, but it is dependent on our strategic ability to protect these systems from cyber threats and attacks on their privacy. IRIS addresses this challenge with a collaborative-first approach centered around CERTs/CSIRTs. From a technological perspective, it deploys (i) autonomous detection of IoT and AI threats, enriched with (ii) privacy-aware intelligence sharing and collaboration, and (iii) advanced data protection and accountability. Crucially, IRIS introduces (iv) the first dedicated online training and cyber exercises to prepare CERTs/CSIRTs to collaboratively protect critical infrastructures and systems against cross-

border AI and IoT threats. IRIS will be validated in three pilot demonstrators, focussing in the IoT, AI and cross[1]border dimensions, across three existing smart city environments (in Helsinki, Tallinn and Barcelona), involving the associated national/governmental CERTs/CSIRTs, cybersecurity authorities and municipalities. The scenarios will contain real-life inspired cyber incidents that will build up into pilots at all levels (from local to national and to cross[1]border) to showcase the versatility of the IRIS solution. With 19 key partners from around Europe and 5 CERTs/CSIRTs as Associated Partners, IRIS's solid consortium composition and work plan prioritises the effectiveness needed for quick real-world adoption and impact. Moreover, integration will be carried out on the EU's existing MeliCERTes platform, with the support of INTRASOFT, while training will build upon THALES's existing cyber range, and ECSO will ensure the contribution to standards and policymaking. With the formal support of the four H2020 Cybersecurity Competence Network Pilot Projects, IRIS will also actively engage with the full scope of the cybersecurity ecosystem in Europe.

IRIS Typefaces

The primary typeface is Futura with a secondary Open Sans font to complement the primary. These two typefaces have been carefully selected to give prominence to the brand image, and must be always used to retain consistency - especially within the logo. Replacing fonts with alternatives should not be done under any circumstances. It is strongly recommended for consistency reasons to use these two typefaces for any type of IRIS promotional material and in web media and applications

Primary Typeface

Futura

AaBbCcDdEe 1 2 3

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

£!@#\$%^&*()_+=[]{};'\.,/:" | <>?

Light AaBbCcDdEe 1 2 3

Book AaBbCcDdEe 1 2 3

Medium AaBbCcDdEe 1 2 3

Bold AaBbCcDdEe 1 2 3

IRIS Typefaces

Secondary font

The Open Sans font should be used in all printed materials that are editable and can be sent outside of IRIS in an editable form.

For all Official IRIS documents (i.e. memo, agreement, forms, etc.) the font size should be 11.

Open Sans is available on most computers, as it is a system font.

Secondary font

Font weights

Open Sans supports most of the languages.

Open Sans

AaBbCcDdEe123

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
£!@#\$\$%^&*()_+ -=[]{};'\,./:" | <>?

Light AaBbCcDdEe123

Regular AaBbCcDdEe123

SemiBold AaBbCcDdEe123

Bold AaBbCcDdEe123

Extrabold AaBbCcDdEe123

IRIS

Do's and Dont's

Display the IRIS logo only in the forms specified in this guide. The IRIS logo may not appear in any colour. Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, reproduce, alter or distort the IRIS logo in any way.

Do not combine the IRIS logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

- ✓ Always use logo files from the Brand Guidelines respective folders. Never try to recreate them from the guidelines.

- ✗ Never stray from the color palette

- ✗ Never rearrange elements of the design

- ✗ Never stretch or distort the Logo

- ✗ Never change or alter any fonts.

- ✗ Never change the orientation of the logo with angles different than 0 or 90

IRIS

Logo variations

Positive

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. This primary format is used in every occasion except from the cases it is not feasible. In these cases, the following versions are available for usage:

Negative

This format of the IRIS logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a colored background or a pattern.

Greyscale

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e. internal memos).

Positive

This is the primary format of the IRIS logo and is used in every occasions except from the ones specifically mentioned in this guide

Greyscale

Greyscale logos are for use in printed black and white publications such as newspapers. They are also used for internal documents that you know will be printed on black and white printers such as internal memos.

Negative

This format of the IRIS logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a colored background or a pattern.

IRIS Logo usage

Safe area is used to prevent from placing other elements near the logo that may distort the perception of the sign. The module used to determine the safe area around logo is the width of the letter “C”.

Clear space

The Clear Space has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the IRIS logotype. Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the IRIS logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals.

Print Size

2 cm X 1,9 cm

Screen size

107 px X 102 px

Minimum size

The Minimum size has been carefully determined to ensure that the IRIS logo is reproduced correctly in smaller sizes. At Minimum size, the logo is still clearly legible and easily identifiable. When using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

IRIS Logo Usage on backgrounds

When placing the logo on an image, color or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

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